

Scaling and Handling of Time in Plane Waves in a Potential

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In (1) (2), an expression for f_p , the momentum wavefunction, for a particle in a box with no potential (except at the walls) is given. Here $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, where $W(x)$ is the spatial wavefunction. The description given suggests that even for a “free” particle in a box, there are all possible momentum states with $E = (\hbar k)^2/2m$ being an average energy. The spatial wavefunction is proportional to $\sin(kx - b(n))$ where $b(n)$ is a constant depending on n , the energy level and the center of the box is at $x=0$. The spatial result is interesting because it seems one is considering $\exp(ipx + i p^2/2m t)$ scattering from the walls to create a resonance, which is of the same form ($\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$) as the constituent plane waves except now one has k which is the root mean square momentum. The energy also scales from $p^2/2m$ for each plane wave to an overall average E .

In this note, we try to investigate this behaviour for a particle in a box and for other potentials and consider issues in handling $\exp(ip^2/2m t)$. For a plane wave, time and space are linked in $px - p^2/2m t$, but in a quantum resonance things seem to be different. Finally, we suggest that since it is possible to have $\exp(ipx + p^2/2m t)$ states combine to form an overall new $\exp(ikx + Et)$ where E is the average energy and k the root mean square momentum, it may be that $\exp(ipx + ip^2/2m t)$ for a quantum particle is also of the same form. In other words, a quantum particle may have internal motion and components which lead to the $\exp(ipx + ip^2/2m t)$ result with p being a root mean square momentum of internal components and $p^2/2m$ an average energy. In a previous note (3), it was suggested Einstein’s energy-momentum equation $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$ where $c=1$ leads to a backward and forward motion as a particle moves forward with average velocity v . It was suggested that such motion might be modeled by $\exp(ipx + ip^2/2m t)$.

Plane Wave Modeling of the Schrodinger Equation

In a previous note (4), it was suggested that the time-independent Schrodinger equation represents a kind of in-phase averaging of plane waves which scatter from a potential to create an average energy at each x point which equals E i.e. the classical energy.

$$\left[\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ i.e. is a normalization constant called the wavefunction and $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. It should be noted there is no time in ((1)) and the $\exp(ipx)$ do not carry a phase. One may argue that if one wants a certain parity, say an even function then $f_p = f_{-p}$. Also, one requires a real solution as there is not net translational flux. For a particle in a box, $v(x) = \text{constant}$ and ((1)) is of the form of a differential equation:

$$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W]/W = .5 m v^*v$$

So $\exp(i mv x)$ and $\exp(-imv x)$ are solutions as is $\cos(mv x)$ (even function case). Thus, classical kinetic energy is governing the problem, which is in turn dependent on the potential through $.5 mv^*v = E-V(x)$. E , the classical energy, is an average quantum energy and $mv(x)$, the classical momentum, a root mean square quantum momentum. Time is not included in ((1)) because it does not govern the resonance in a spatial sense. If one were to add $\exp(i p^*p/2mt)$ as a factor to every $\exp(ipx)$ one would have spreading in time as in a wavepacket which would destroy the resonance. Furthermore, the particle is continually scattering and different p collisions with the potential take different amounts of time to occur so it does not seem that including $\exp(ip^*p/2m t)$ makes sense.

If, on the other hand, the scattering of plane waves is reasonable, it seems one should be able to formulate the problem in terms of time alone, i.e. use $\exp(i p^*p/2m t)$ without $\exp(ipx)$. We use the weights $g(E)$.

$$[\text{Sum over } E g(E) \exp(i E/2m t)] / [\text{Sum over } E g(E) \exp(i E t)] = .5m v(x)v(x) \quad ((2))$$

For $v(x)=\text{constant}$, one has the solution $\exp(iEt)$ from quantum mechanics, so $g(E)$ and fp are strongly linked. In other words, it is not only $\exp(ipx)$'s which combine to form an overall $\sin(kx - b(x))$, but the $\exp(ip^*p/2m t)$ also do a similar thing to create an overall $\exp(iE t)$.

In the general case of $V(x)$ not zero for a range of x , one should also be able to write an equation for $\exp(ip^*p/2m t)$ i.e. ((2)). If x is held constant, then one again obtains the solution of:

$$d/dt Q(t) = .5 m v(x)v(x) Q(t) \text{ where } x=\text{constant. Here } Q(t)=[\text{Sum over } E g(E) \exp(i E t)] \quad ((3))$$

The solution is $\exp(i .5m v(x)v(x) t)$ in all cases. For the case of $v(x)$ varying with x , one sees that the $Q(t)$ also varies with x . Thus, there is a different frequency at each x point. If one suggests there should only be one frequency which holds for every x , this may be obtained by adding $V(x)$ to the exponent of $Q(t)$. Then, one has $\exp(iEt)$ which seems to be the quantum resonance result.

Scaling

For a particle in a box, one may combine $\exp(ipx)$ plane waves to obtain an overall spatial wavefunction of $\sin(kx - b(n))$ where k is the root mean square momentum and separately combine $\exp(ip^*p/2m t)$ to obtain an overall $\exp(iEt)$ where E is the average energy. It seems there is a kind of scaling occurring. It is suggested this scaling might exist at the internal level of the quantum particle. In other words, for $\exp(ipx + i Et)$, p might also be a root mean square momentum and E and average energy for internal motion. It is suggested in (3), that one can solve Einstein's energy-momentum equation as a 2x2 matrix, linear in E . This leads to a two

vector with the upper component representing forward motion and the lower, backward. Thus, a quantum particle may undergo a type of zitterbewegung, moving back and forth while moving with an average v in the forward direction. This has also been suggested by others in the literature using different arguments. Alternatively, one may consider motion of internal components of a quantum particle. Thus, it may be that the use of $\exp(ipx + iEt)$ at the basic level of quantum particles, has a deeper root, and p and $E=p^2/2m$ may be linked to average values. This is interesting as it leads to questions about energy. For the zitterbewegung particle of (3), the average classical momentum is mv , but there is forward and backward motion which contributes to both the kinetic energy and the velocity dependent mass energy.

Conclusion

The idea of using plane waves scattering from a potential seems to even apply to a quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls. The plane waves $\exp(ipx + i p^2/2m t)$, which seem to be the starting point for quantum mechanics, combine or scale to produce an overall wavefunction with a time portion of $\exp(iEt)$ where E is the average energy and a spatial portion $\sin(kx + b(n))$ where k is the root mean square momentum. Thus, it is suggested $\exp(ipx + i p^2/2m t)$ itself may be the scaled (averaged) result of internal motion of the quantum particle. Furthermore, it is suggested that when using plane wave scattering for a bound system, one either describes the problem in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ with time removed or in terms of $\exp(ip^2/2m t)$ with $\exp(ipx)$ removed. In the later case, one obtains an overall time result of $Q(t)= \exp(i .5mv(x)v(x) t)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. To have a constant frequency at each point x , one may add $V(x)$ to the exponent of $Q(t)$. (This may have consequences on a wavepacket as one usually adds $ip^2/2m t$ to each plane wave in the packet instead of treating the time and spatial portions separately and assuming a kind of interaction leading from $\exp(ipx)$ to another.)

References

1. Majernik, V and Majernikova, E. The Momentum Entropy of the Infinite Well (Journal of Physics General Physics 1999)
file:///home/chronos/u-8dd8a372933f68c28035cee18f7c4c1f27fe9a76/Downloads/diplomka.pdf
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230930491>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2018)